

Abstract

Socio - Economic and Health Status of Child Rag-pickers in Mumbai

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Abstract: Uncontrolled waste accumulation in big cities has become major threat to urban health. Over the past half-century, waste picking has expanded vastly in developing world due to urbanization (Wilson et al. 2005). Existence of rag-pickers represents nexus of poverty, inequality and lack of proper city planning. Although it is hazardous for children, rag-picking is usually a more lucrative option than other menial labour as it requires no special knowledge; hence they prefer it over other works (Baker, 2000). Studies on street children briefly mention about numbers of child rag-pickers, but there is no study to present exact numbers and situation of child rag pickers. Further, there are scarce studies available on health status of child rag-pickers. A comprehensive study covering socio – economic and health related aspects with respect to child rag - a picker is missing in literature. **Objective:** The current study aims to describe demographic and socioeconomic status, current health status, and utilization of health care by child rag-pickers. **Methods:** A total of 225 child rag pickers of age 8 to 17 years, who work on dumping grounds in Mumbai, were covered in the study. Using structured interview schedule the data on background characteristics, working conditions, self-reported illnesses over last one year, treatment seeking by respondents was collected. A bi-variate technique was used for the analysis and findings were presented using descriptive statistics. Outcome variable i.e. self-reported major illness was correlated with independent variables, and the association between occupation related morbidity has been described. **Results:** It is found that there were 222 boys working on dumping ground and three girls child rag pickers. Majority of respondents (73.3 per cent) were Muslims. About 74 per cent of respondents did not know their castes. Ninety seven per cent of respondents lived near dumping ground. Their family's mean income was Rs. 7534.3 per month. At mean age of 10.7 years respondents started working on dumping ground. Child rag-pickers very often suffer from minor illnesses, which if ignored may lead to major illness that needs hospitalization. Due to higher cost at private hospitals most of respondents (75.6 per cent) had preferred public health facilities. About 90 per cent of respondents got denied access in public health care facility. Majority of (97.5 per cent) were asked to pay bribe for admission in hospitals. Most of respondents were dissatisfied with quality of treatment they received in public health posts. Ninety eight per cent respondents did not get quality care in public health center. **Conclusion:** Study revealed that child rag very often get exposed to occupational hazards and do not have any access to social security schemes and financial support for taking treatment.

Citation: Tikhute, V. (2020). Socio - Economic and Health Status of Child Rag-pickers in Mumbai. National Seminar on Population, Health and Sustainable Development Goals: Performance and Prioritizing Policies (IIPS National Seminar 2020), PRC, Patna University, Patna, Bihar. International Institute for Population Sciences (IIPS) and University of Patna. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408665>

Received: 15 Dec 2019

Revised: 30 Dec 2019

Accepted: 21 Jan 2019

Published: 15 Feb 2020

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Keywords: child rag-picker; major illnesses; morbidity; treatment seeking; working conditions